

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Deliverable D3.1

PARC website

WP 3

Partnership
FOR THE
Assessment
OF
Risks
FROM
Chemicals

Co-funded by
the European Union

This partnership has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 101057014.

Partnership
FOR THE
Assessment
OF
Risks
FROM
Chemicals

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

This partnership has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 101057014.

Technical reference

Work package	WP3 - Synergies, collaborations and awareness
Task	T3.2 - Communication, dissemination, and awareness
Dissemination level 1	PU
Lead Beneficiary/ Responsible AE	EEA, NPHC
Contributing Participants	-
Responsible author(s)	Roser Gasol, EEA, roser.gasol@eea.europa.eu Tamás Szigeti, NPHC, szigeti.tamas@nnk.gov.hu
Co-authors	Aglaia Koutsodimou, GCSL, a.koutsodimou@aade.gr Eugenia Dessipri, GCSL, e.desipri@aade.gr Maria João Silva, INSA, m.joao.silva@insa.min-saude.pt Sónia Namorado, INSA, sonia.namorado@insa.min-saude.pt
Reviewers	Pascal Sanders, ANSES, pascal.sanders@anses.fr Christophe Rousselle, ANSES, christophe.rousselle@anses.fr Marie Conort, ANSES, marie.conort@anses.fr Basile Cazalis de Fondouce, ANSES, basile.cazalisdefondouce@anses.fr
Due date of deliverable	31 July 2022
Actual submission date	22 March 2023

1 PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other program participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

Version	Date	Reviewer name/Institutions	Short description of changes
version 1	8 March 2023		

Abstract

The website is one of the main communication channels applied in the PARC project. The main aims of the development of the website and the structure of the PARC website (<https://www.eu-parc.eu/>) are described in this deliverable. The website was officially launched in February 2023. New features and content will be added until the end of the partnership.

Keywords

website, communication, dissemination, awareness

5 “Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

Table of contents

Technical reference	3
Document history	4
Abstract	5
Keywords	5
1. Development of the PARC website	7
1.1. Background	7
1.2. The PARC website	7
1.3. Planned developments	12

1. Development of the PARC website

1.1. Background

One of the main activities covered by T3.2 is to develop and maintain the PARC website by following the latest online standards in web development. The project website is the main shop window and will showcase a complete overview of the project. The main aims of the website development are the following:

- provide information on the project, the management, contact points,
- create an online space for the dissemination of project results including research outputs, new tools and methods, indicators,
- promote the PARC project to a broad range of end users and external audiences by introducing high level of user-friendliness and user experience on the website,
- serve the consortium partners, policy makers, regulators and different stakeholders.

1.2. The PARC website

The PARC website was officially launched on 17th February 2023 and available at <https://www.eu-parc.eu/>. The website is in line with the PARC communication and dissemination strategy (D3.2) and the visual identity guidelines developed in the framework of the project.

The working language of the website is English. There is a main menu and also a top menu on the left. A footer with access to the same section from the main menu is also published to give the possibility to access the same section from different entry points.

The following elements are included on the website:

- what we do:
 - mission, vision and objectives,
 - our impact,
- thematic areas:
 - risk assessment,
 - tools & resources,
 - building capacities,
 - science to policy,
- news & events,
- about us:
 - our story,

DELIVERABLE

- governance,
- contacts list,
- PARC in figures,
- newsletters,
- media,
- contact us.

The links to the PARC social media channels are also available on the website.

Some screenshots are depicted in the following figures.

Fig. 1. Animated logo on the homepage

Fig. 2. "What we do" section on the homepage with two short articles

Fig. 3. Content of the “What we do” section together with a graphical element

Fig. 4. Presentation of the four thematic areas on the homepage

Fig. 5. News items on the homepage

Fig. 6. Visualization of the main numbers of the project

ABOUT US

- Our story
- Governance
- Contacts list

Use the interactive map above to discover the governance structure of P-A-R-C.

Fig. 7. Interactive governance structure

PARC Newsletter

PARC is a joint effort of 28 countries and three EU agencies, co-funded by Horizon Europe. The main aim of the partnership is to develop next-generation chemical risk assessment to protect human health and the environment.

First Name

Last Name

Email *

Organisation type

Opt in to another list

PARC Science Digest

European Environment Agency's News Service

I agree to be emailed*

I agree to have my email activity tracked

[Link to EEA's Privacy Policy](#)

PARC Science Digest

PARC is a joint effort of 28 countries and three EU agencies, co-funded by Horizon Europe. The main aim of the partnership is to develop next-generation chemical risk assessment to protect human health and the environment. You will receive the PARC monthly Science Digest.

Name

Surname

Email *

Opt in to another list

PARC Newsletter

European Environment Agency's News Service

I agree to EEA's Privacy Policy*

I agree to have my response to EEA and PARC newsletters tracked (for example open newsletter, link clicks and city location)

[Link to Privacy Policy](#)

Fig. 8. Online form for the subscription of the newsletters

Fig. 9. PARC media kit on the website

1.3. Planned developments

The website is under development and the following new features will be added in April 2023:

- interactive map showing the consortium members,
- scientific publications with details and filtering option,
- SYNnet contact forms to establish synergies,
- PARC indicators,
- News and event section,
- Detailed description of the thematic areas.